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LAB-IN-A-BOX: PRELIMINARY FINDINGS OF A PROFESSIONAL LEARNING EXPERIENCE FOR TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

In the USA, the National Science Foundation (NSF) funds Research Experience for Teachers (RET) programs where teachers have the opportunity to contribute to ongoing research projects in the setting of institutions of higher education. RET programs are usually held in person during summer over several weeks. In this paper, we describe a virtual RET program, called Portable Lab RET, piloted by NSF Nanosystems Engineering Research Center (ERC) for Nanomanufacturing Systems for Mobile Computing and Mobile Energy Technologies (NASCENT) at the University of Texas, Austin during the summer 2020, in response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

During the two-week long Portable Lab RET program, teachers performed two real-world scientific experiments using pre-made lab kits deployed to their homes. For each lab kit, teachers discussed and shared ideas with NASCENT faculty and staff and other RET participants about different ways to implement and adapt them to their classrooms.

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The 2020 RET program was attended by 5 participants, math, science and engineering teachers from local school districts. Data were collected through Zoom interviews a few weeks after the end of the program. Overall, participants enjoyed the experience and offered meaningful suggestions on how to improve it. Teachers developed ideas to adapt the lab kits to one or more of their curricular units and to engage their students in directly interacting with the kits. We believe that the collaboration between university researchers and K-12 teachers afforded by the lab kits could bridge the gap between these two worlds.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context Background

In the United States, the Next Generation Science Standards push for a redesigned K-12 science education where students are actively engaged in real world scientific problems. Professional Learning Experiences (PLEs) that encourage the development and understanding of scientific and engineering practices aim to support teachers in the implementation of these new standards. However, it is important to distinguish the key components of quality PLE among the vast array of opportunities available. According to Wilson [1] key factors for successful science PLE are: engaging teachers in active learning, alignment with standard reforms, providing activities that are close to practice and immersing teachers in inquiry experiences. PLEs need to provide numerous opportunities for educators to experience activities in a fashion similar to how they will present them to their students [2, 3] and focus on inquiry experiences [4, 5]. Indeed, Garet et al. [6] reported that it is important for PLE to focus on duration, collective participation and content with opportunities for hands-on work to have an impact on teaching practices.

Among the many PLEs available, the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) funds Research Experience for Teachers (RET) programs [7] where teachers have the opportunity to experience scientific research and learn “how to do science” in the setting of institutions of higher education. RET programs are usually held in the summer, lasting several weeks, when local teachers participate to ongoing research projects under the supervision of graduate students and faculty members through daily laboratory work. Several studies have shown that the collaboration between scientists and educators leads to gains in teachers' understanding of scientific inquiry and increased use of inquiry-based lessons [8-10] and hands-on classroom activities [11]. Other benefits connected to the RET format include the use of real-world interdisciplinary applications, increased exposure to engineering processes [12] and the opportunity to build a community of like-minded teachers, scientists and engineering professionals [13, 14].

In this paper, we describe a new kind of RET program developed by the NSF Nanosystems Engineering Research Center (ERC) for Nanomanufacturing Systems for Mobile Computing and Mobile Energy Technologies (NASCENT) at the University of Texas, Austin, during the summer 2020, called the Portable Lab RET program. NASCENT is a research center funded by the NSF that, parallel to its research, organizes a variety of educational outreach programs for undergraduates, graduates and elementary, middle and high school teachers. The Portable Lab program was piloted during the summer 2020 in response to the COVID-19 pandemic that forced a

drastic change in how the RET program could be delivered. NASCENT took this challenge as an opportunity to reimagine the RET program to be completely online with the goal to possibly expand it to teachers across the country. Drawing from the in-person RET, it was important to include a research component to afford teachers the opportunity to experience and take back to the classroom first-hand knowledge of scientific research and engineering practices.

The Portable Lab RET program employs pre-made lab kits that are deployed to teachers' homes and support is provided through an online platform. Teachers perform scientific experiments following detailed instructions, while reviewing scientific concepts through seminars and reading materials. Each week, together with NASCENT faculty and staff and other RET participants, teachers have the opportunity to discuss possible applications of the lab kits to fit them into their curriculum. Current research that examines PLEs and their impact on teachers' learning indicates that enabling teachers to be active learners and co-designers of a PLE supports the growth of interdisciplinary, active classroom teaching [15]. During the Portable Lab RET program, each teacher contributes to the discussion by bringing their preexisting subject-matter and pedagogical content knowledge and background and by applying the new concepts and pedagogy learned during the program. Teachers become essential contributors and leaders of the PLE and, leveraging their expertise, they are able to build on each other's ideas to propose multiple ways to adapt the lab kits to a curricular unit and to engage their students in interacting activities.

This preliminary study aims to investigate how teachers respond and interact with these new tools and their plans to incorporate the lab kits in their classroom activities. In this paper, we will first describe the portable labs and the theoretical framework used to design this study and the research questions. In the methods section, we will provide a brief description of the program, report on the methods used for data collection and results; we will then conclude with a discussion of findings, highlighting implications and plans for future research on this topic.

1.2 Portable Labs

The lab kits used in this project were originally developed as part of university-level coursework and later adapted for use with teachers. The efforts to expand the use of lab kits into the school system involves planning experiments that would enhance the already-taught school curriculum. Choosing and designing the lab involved the following aspects:

- The labs have to be part of a coherent curriculum.
- The simplified hardware should allow students to acquire practical knowledge in a short term and grasp the basic theory, incentivizing them to seek deeper information at their own discretion.
- The experiments should contain quantitative components where the students have to measure values and report them. This aspect elevates the experience from a general demonstration.
- The experiments have to be robust and the hardware should be reliable. When designing the experimental procedure, we try to mitigate possibilities of incorrect assembly. For example, we make sure the quantities of materials applied are within comfortable range so a few drops more, or less, of added

material will not affect the experiment. We set the results to be well within the detecting and measuring ranges of our devices.

- Safety in a residential setting should be a priority. Participants conduct the experiments in their homes rather than in a lab or chemical hood. For example, participants should not be expected to handle toxic materials or dispose of toxic waste.

Within these considerations in mind, we designed the lab modules as self-standing; manuals include concise and clear instructions and some theoretical background to execute the experiment. To keep safety in the forefront, each manual includes safety instructions and a quiz for the user to test knowledge of safety protocols prior to conducting the experiment. Lastly, in order to mass produce the lab kits, their cost cannot exceed US\$100 (approximately 84€) each.

The two lab kits employed during the 2020 Portable RET included the following experiments:

- Spin coating lab kit: participants built a spin coater and deposit a thin organic film on a silicon wafer. Then they deduced the thickness of the film according to the color caused by interference.
- Particle contamination lab kit: participants learned about scattering of light by nanoparticle suspensions. They let various lasers run through gold and silica nanoparticle suspensions and determined the sizes of the nanoparticles.

For each lab kit, the manual includes detailed photos and step-by-step instructions.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in a cognitive perspective on teaching and teacher learning [16, 17]. This perspective explains teaching as a way of relying on different categories of knowledge in sensemaking while interacting with a new tool or assimilating a new idea. *Knowledge* is the broad term referring to mental structures, consisting of mental representations and processes that act on them [18].

This theoretical framework has an important implication for the study of teachers' approach and experience with the lab kits and for the way they adapt them in their classroom. With the assumption that teachers come from a wide range of backgrounds, they approached the lab kits in different ways depending on their subject matter knowledge, the discipline that they teach and the related pedagogical content knowledge, and their experience with the grade level of their students. In particular, it is worthwhile to analyze whether the teachers' preexisting knowledge and the support materials provided during the program were sufficient for the teachers' development of the related content knowledge. Also, while proceeding through the experiment, teachers reflected and elaborated on plans to incorporate the lab kit in their classroom. Since science and engineering teachers may have more experience with lab and hands-on activities compared to math teachers who may have a more traditional approach to teaching (teaching spectrum), the plan to use the lab kits in the classroom may vary from a live-experiment to a demo.

The intent of this study is to analyze the interaction of teachers with the lab kits, understand the impactful factors that shape this interaction and document the different ways teachers envision the use of the lab kits in their classrooms and their students engaging with them.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions investigated in this paper are:

- What was the overall teachers' experience with the lab kits and the RET online format?
- How do teachers plan to adapt the lab kits to their curricular needs?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Program description

The Portable Lab RET program is a two week-long online program. Teachers independently performed the experiments in the two lab kits supported by NASCENT faculty and staff through an online platform. Together with the two labs, participants received a safety guide and instructional manuals.

Each week, teachers attended three days of lectures and seminars and two days of curriculum mapping and ideas sharing in the morning and worked on the experiments in the afternoon with the online support of NASCENT graduate students. The schedule of the two weeks is reported in Table 1. For each lab, participants reviewed the manual and instruction material with the graduate students supervising the experiment and took a pre-lab safety quiz which was a prerequisite before moving forward with the experiment. At the end of each experiment, the teachers took an assessment quiz (multiple choice questions).

Table 1: RET 2020 Schedule

	Lectures (10am-12pm)	Labs (1:30 - 4:00 pm)
1st week		
Day 1	History of miniaturization, micro- and nano-technologies, electronics, healthcare, etc.	
Day 2	Coating and lithography	Spin-coating lab: go over lab manual, pre-lab quiz
Day 3	Nanodevices overview	Participants work on the spin-coating lab
Day 4	Discuss mapping to curriculum	Participants complete spin-coating lab
Day 5	Discuss mapping to curriculum	Participants complete post-lab quiz
2nd Week		
Day 1	Nanoparticle fabrication and properties	Nanoparticle lab: go over lab manual, pre-lab quiz
Day 2	Nanobiotechnology	Participants work and complete nanoparticle lab
Day 3	Nanotech and big data	RETs complete post-lab quiz
Day 4	Discuss mapping to curriculum	Example of student lab activity
Day 5	Discuss Future labs	

The 2020 Portable Lab RET program was attended by five participants, four of whom agreed to participate in this research study: one middle school math teacher, one middle school science teachers, one high school math teacher and one middle school engineering teacher. Among the four participants in this study, two attended the in-person RET at NASCENT in prior years. It is typical for teachers to participate multiple years.

2.2 Data Collection and Analysis

The Portable Lab RET program ran from July 6-17, 2020. Teachers participating in this program were employees of two neighboring school districts in the Austin (Texas, USA) area. At the end of August, RET participants were contacted via email to check their availability for an interview. Four participants out of five agreed to the interview.

The semi-structured interviews were held online through Zoom and lasted approximately 45 min. Each participant was interviewed individually, following the same semi-structured protocol, and a consent form was signed by each interviewee. The protocol included three broad areas of questions:

1. experience with the kit and with the program: teachers were asked questions concerning the use of the kit, the clarity of the manual and instructions received and their satisfaction with program format;
2. classroom application: teachers were asked to describe their vision concerning the use the lab kit in the classroom and the possible impact of this experience on their students;
3. suggestions about expanding the program in the future.

Interviews were recorded and transcribed. Inductive coding by the first author under the supervision of another author was used to address the research questions posed in this paper. An Institutional Research Board (i.e., ethics) approved protocol (Federal Wide Assurance of Compliance # 00002030) governs data analysis and publication.

3 RESULTS

3.1 RQ 1: What was the overall teachers' experience with the lab kits and the RET online format?

Overall, all the teachers enjoyed the experience of working with the lab kits.

One teacher, who previously experienced the in-person format and loved it, felt that the online format needed some adjustments. Another teacher who previously attended the in-person format felt that the online format was equally successful, and they would highly recommend it. This latter teacher felt that expanding the program to teachers from other areas will bring new ideas, allowing collaboration across multiple geographic areas and different disciplines.

Teachers reported that instruction manuals were clear, but some grammar edits are needed to improve readability and some photos need to be replaced to match the experiment as closely as possible; this is seen of particular importance for students' use of the lab kits. Seminars and lectures were very useful, but teachers suggested breaking down lectures into mini lectures or slowing the pace to allow time to absorb the material. For example, one teacher suggested changing the schedule to mini lectures and embed discussion into them. Another expressed preference towards a PLE delivered in a fashion similar to the kind of structure that will be used for students, for

example synchronous/whole class session of approximately 40-45min with the addition of asynchronous/independent work time to allow for breaks from the computer. Teachers were very pleased with the guidance received and they felt that the afternoon format when teacher performed the experiment guided by NASCENT graduate students was successful. However, due to the different backgrounds, some teachers expressed the need for additional guidance and supporting material.

During the interviews, all the teachers reported how finding themselves in the role of the learner impacted them. The teachers expressed a renewed empathy and understanding towards their students and the frustration they experience while challenged with new concepts. One teacher suggested adding a “pep-talk” in the schedule to help maintain a positive attitude and to support teachers in coping with the possible frustration of the challenges of “being the student”.

3.2 RQ 2: How do teachers plan to adapt the lab kits to their curricular needs?

Teachers reported that the main appeal of the kits is engaging their students in the experiments. They planned creative ways to use the lab kits in their classroom, adapting them to the subject they teach and the specific curricular constraints they face, with some teachers having more curricular flexibility than others due to state government requirements and testing.

Moreover, each teacher presented a different perspective based on their area of expertise and interests. For example, one of the math teachers planned to challenge students to find patterns and perform statistical analysis of the data; this math teacher seemed enthusiastic to show their students that “mathematics isn’t just in a textbook” and to bring “real world mathematics in the classroom”. The engineering teacher examined ways to include the kit in an engineering design project; they are planning to incorporate the spin coating lab in the building of a solar cell and the particle contamination project in the creation of a water filtration system for the local creek.

At the time of the interviews, it was still unclear when schools in the area were going to reopen in-person, the number of students attending in-person and what constraints were going to be imposed to the in-person teaching. When discussing possible options to use the lab kits with their students, teachers weighted the possibilities of working in-person or online. If schools resume in-person, their goal is to have students directly interact with the kits; teachers discussed sharing two-three lab kits per class and creating rotation stations giving each student the opportunity to manipulate the kits. According to the teachers, the benefit of the lab kits in the classroom is more than the specific science concepts; students will experience real science and be inspired by the sense of discovery. One teacher felt that the biggest takeaway was “the idea that a project doesn’t have to be focused on math or on the content for it to be beneficial; if it adds to students’ interests and students’ engagement then it’s adding to the course”. In the case of online school, some teachers were planning video demonstrations; according to teachers, demonstrations are not ideal since they take away from the tactile and interactive experience, but they would still be interesting for students.

When asked in what ways this program changed their teaching practices, only one teacher replied that it didn’t because they felt that their teaching approach is already hands-on. One teacher replied that it helped in bringing 21st century technology in the classroom; another hoped to better relate with the students having experienced the discomfort of being in the learner seat, and another teacher replied that they feel more

inclined to use lab kits to bring the real world in the classroom while teaching mathematics.

An interesting observation came from a teacher who attended the in-person program twice in previous years. The teacher felt that the two prior in-person RET experiences were very powerful because the teacher worked with researchers and observe and learn from them and was given the opportunity to create their own lab. According to this teacher, the online format took away “the creative outlet” because it consisted in learning to follow tasks instead of creating a lab to use in class. “It felt that something at the university level was forced in the curriculum” while the goal is to learn “what scientists do at the university level and teach it to my kids. Teachers have the expertise to bridge university research with school curriculum.”

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Overall, all the teachers enjoyed the experience of working with the lab kits, in particular because of the subsequent opportunity to engage their students with them in the classroom.

To answer research question 1, about the overall teachers’ experience with the lab kits during the program, teachers were asked questions concerning the material and support received and the clarity of the tasks assigned. Participants made the suggestion of administering a PLE that is similar to what they will present to their students with short lectures and time for breaks; this finding is in line with literature studies on the characteristics of effective PLEs [2, 3]. Additional attention should be given to the teachers’ existing content knowledge in order to provide adequate support and material and allow completion of the tasks and deep understanding of the science behind the experiment. Finding the middle ground between a rigorous scientific experiment and the need to accommodate a variety of science backgrounds is an important goal for NASCENT. Additionally, teachers reported an increased ability to better relate to their students, having experienced the frustration and discomfort of learning new and challenging concepts.

To answer research question 2, about teachers’ plans to adapt the lab kits to their curricular needs, participants were asked questions concerning ways to include the lab kits in one or more curricular units and how they envision their students engaging with the lab kits. Participants discussed creative plans to incorporate the lab kits in their classrooms, including teachers of subjects “usually not hands-on”. One teacher lamented the limitations to the creativity due to the use of the pre-made lab kit while others have welcomed the opportunity to bring real world applications into the classroom. Reflecting of these observations, we believe that although the online format uses premade lab kits, taking away the creativity to make a personal research project, they afford teachers and students the opportunity to manipulate equipment as in an actual lab (in a similar fashion as scientists do). Indeed, participants reported that they believe their students will engage with the lab kits and will be inspired and excited by the sense of discovery and the ability to do “real science”. Moreover, due to the vital involvement of the teachers in adapting the lab kits to their curricular units, these projects intend to leverage on teachers’ expertise to bridge the gap between university research and K-12 teaching. The lab kits have the potential to give teachers the flexibility to adjust them to their curricular needs.

All the participants except one – whose teaching style is already “hands-on” - felt that the program had an impact on their teaching practices, from bringing 21st century technology in the classroom to real world scientific applications to ability to better relate with students’ frustration when dealing with difficult concepts. Future investigation of classroom implementation of lab kits related materials will help determine the impact of this program on teaching practices.

5 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This study presents preliminary findings related to the evaluation of a pilot RET virtual program developed in response to the challenges presented by the COVID-19 pandemic. The results from this first session are encouraging in terms of participants’ satisfaction and impact that the lab kits could have on teachers and students across the country. The multi-disciplinary application of the lab is, in our opinion, the strength of the lab kits together with the collaboration that they create between the research world and the K-12 world.

However, the small sample size doesn’t allow for generalization and, although classroom plans to use the lab kits have been discussed in detail during the interviews, investigation of classroom implementation is needed. Future research will focus on students’ interaction with the kits and teachers’ interaction with the kit and with their students in the classroom.

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